

A tale of two OEPs?

Looking at open educational practices
from a policy viewpoint

Leo Havemann, Javiera Atenas *and* Fabio Nascimbeni

#OERxDomains21

A tale of two OEPs? Looking at Open Educational Practices from a policy viewpoint

Leo Havemann, Javiera Atenas and Fabio Nascimbeni (session abstract)

This workshop will engage participants in a discussion of the apparent “understanding gap” between the two OEPs of open educational practices and open education policies, with the aim of ensuring the recognition of existing, successful open practices within appropriate open policies. The starting point of the workshop is the recognition of the distance between much open education policy discourse (often focused on OER, as shown for example by the UNESCO 2019 Recommendation on OER), the research communities working to categorise, replicate and promote a range of grassroots open educational practices (OEP), and the rich variety of actual practices undertaken by educators.

OEP, which were initially understood as teaching approaches that are closely connected to the creation and use of OER (Ehlers 2011), are increasingly being defined more widely, taking in aspects other than open content such as inclusive pedagogies (Havemann 2020), sharing-based approaches (Cronin 2017), care-based teaching methods (Bali, Cronin and Jhangiani 2019) and accessibility dynamics (Tlili et al 2020). In order to explore the different way of understanding openness of the Open Education policy community and the OEP research community, the workshop will engage participants in discussing definitions and perspectives and in co-designing a “policy-sensitive” and “policy-relevant” way to look at OEP, which means classifying OEP from a policy point of view.

Furthermore, we will look at key strategies to support the adoption of the principles of OEP within wider policy and strategic environments in the HE sector, such as digital education, e-learning and open access policies, to ensure that open practices are embedded, supported, enabled and rewarded in line with the academic development programmes, career progression criteria and innovation and teaching excellence schemes. We will invite participants to co-create an action plan and a roadmap following the OE policy co-creation recommendations outlined by Atenas, Havemann, Neumann & Stefanelli (2020), using Mentimeter to crowdsource ideas that can be used to draft guidelines for the inclusion of OEP in HE at policy and strategic levels.

<https://oer21.oerconf.org/a-tale-of-two-oeps-looking-at-open-educational-practices-from-a-policy-viewpoint/>

Introduction

- The open education movement, research and the turn to OEP
- The quest for open education policies
- Our research and work with the OER World Map & OE Policy Hub

Mentimeter activity

- **Which global regions have most OE/OER policies?**
- **What is the most common OE / OER policy scope?**
- **What about the key policy elements by region?**

(based on the oepolicyhub.org data)

Which world region has the most OE or OER policies?

[As voted...]

The data says....

POLICIES BY REGION

Policy scope - which are most prevalent

[As voted...]

The data says....

POLICY SCOPE

KEY POLICY ELEMENT BY REGION

How popular are these open educational practices in your organisation?

To what extent does your organisation have policy OR support in place for...

Mind the gap

- OE policies are still thin on the ground
- OE policies where existing tend to be OER-focused
- OEP include practices that relate to OER but also a wider range of practices

How do we get OE into policy?

Discussion/chat

- **Where should OEP be sitting: in dedicated institutional OER policy, or other policies/strategies (digital learning, education)**
- **Which practices should be included in policies - any that should not be?**

Menti.com code: 2633 1717

Take the OE policy co-creation toolkit home

Here you can get some resources, a timeline, a roadmap, a SWOT and a canvas

Some relevant readings ;)

Havemann, L., Atenas, J., & Neumann, J., (2020). The Open Education policy registry: An open benchlearning tool. OE Policy Working Papers. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3738418>

Atenas, J., Havemann, L., Nascimbeni, F., Villar-Onrubia, D. & Orlic, D. (2019). Fostering Openness in Education: Considerations for Sustainable Policy-Making. <https://openpraxis.org/index.php/OpenPraxis/article/view/947>

Atenas, J., & Havemann, L.. (2021). A review of the OE policy landscape and OE Policy Lab update. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4441190>

Nascimbeni, F., Atenas, J., Basich, P, Aceto, S., Burgos, D. (2017) Policy approaches to Open Education. Case studies from 28 MS <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/policy-approaches-open-education-case-studies-28-eu-member-states-openedu-policies>

Atenas, J., Havemann, L., Neumann, J., & Stefanelli, C.. (2020). OE Policies: Guidelines for co-creation. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4281363>

Stefanelli, C., Atenas, J., Nascimbeni, F., Villar-Onrubia, D. (2020). OpenMed project - OE roadmap <https://openmedproject.eu/home/our-roadmap/>

Timeline

Roadmap

Map the policies you want to review

1

Identify the key issues your institution is facing

3

Draft, review, rewrite and re-review your policy

5

Encourage the participation of underrepresented groups

2

Open co-creation tables to co-create or update a policy

4

Share your policy with the OE community

6

SWOT Analysis

18

STRENGTHS

WEAKNESSES

S

W

O

T

OPPORTUNITIES

THREATS

Open Education Policy Canvas

Co-Creation Process: Describe key proposed stages/events of your co-creation process.

Context: What are the relevant social/cultural issues at play in the policy environment

Policy design partners; Who needs to be involved in the policy co-creation process?

Implementation: Who is needed to implement the policy? What kinds of support are needed?

Stakeholders: Who will benefit from the policy? Who will be affected by the policy?

Policy opportunities: Who is needed to implement the policy? What kinds of support are needed?

Policy challenges
What challenges or barriers does your policy face?

Policy aims: Which are the key aims of your OE policy?

Risks: What could derail your policy?

Who are we?

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References / License

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Atenas, J., Havemann, L., Neumann, J. and Stefanelli, C., 2020. Open Education Policies: Guidelines for co-creation.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4281363>

Bali, M., Cronin, C. and Jhangiani, R.S., 2020. Framing Open Educational Practices from a Social Justice Perspective.

Journal of Interactive Media in Education, 2020(1). <http://doi.org/10.5334/jime.565>

Cronin, C., 2017. Openness and praxis: Exploring the use of open educational practices in higher education.

International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning: IRRODL, 18(5), pp.15-34.

<https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v18i5.3096>

Ehlers, U.D., 2011. Extending the territory: From open educational resources to open educational practices. Journal of Open, Flexible, and Distance Learning, 15(2), pp.1-10.

<http://www.uh.cu/static/documents/RDA/From%20Open%20Educational%20Resources.pdf>

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<http://oro.open.ac.uk/69167>

Tlili, A., Nascimbeni, F., Burgos, D., Zhang, X., Huang, R. and Chang, T.W., 2020. The evolution of sustainability models for Open Educational Resources: insights from the literature and experts. Interactive Learning Environments, pp.1-16.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2020.1839507>